

Biogeographical implications for amphibian conservation in southern Africa

by

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Biogeographical implications for amphibian conservation in southern Africa

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Abstract

Amphibians currently represent the most at-risk as well as the least-conserved vertebrate class on earth and factors contributing to these declines are a subject of active research. However, amphibians present a unique challenge to scientists and conservation managers mainly because of their bi-phasic life cycles. Furthermore, it is now generally accepted that each amphibian life history trait is affected differently by anthropogenic threats. In exploring this aspect further, focusing on the amphibians of the southern African sub-continent, frog species were grouped according to their breeding habitats (stream-, permanent aquatic-, temporary aquatic- and terrestrial-breeding groups). First, using a random draw technique focusing specifically on South Africa, at both the national and the biogeographical scales (the latter being defined as sub-regions within the study area identified based on similarities in frog species distributions; see Chapter 2); I evaluate whether areas where different frog breeding-groups occur are characterised by higher levels of anthropogenic threats (human population density, percentage land transformation, percentage protected area, and invasive alien plant richness) than expected by chance. Terrestrial-breeders were often spatially congruent with areas of high threat than expected by chance at both national and biogeographical scales with land

transformation and invasive alien plant richness being most significant. Areas where stream-breeders occur were spatially congruent with anthropogenic threats (with alien plants being most consistent) in five of the seven regions examined while protected areas were well-represented in four of the seven regions. Non-significant results were found for permanent and temporary aquatic-breeders at both national and biogeographic scales. Second, I then evaluated the relationship between different frog breeding-group richness and the proportion of protected areas per grid cell (i.e., the proportion of the grid cell that constitutes protected land) and how this relationship is affected by controlling for the wider unprotected matrix. I found that the current southern African conservation portfolio (that is, all proclaimed statutory conservation areas of the sub-continent) only moderately captures anuran distributions. I found a negative relationship between terrestrial-breeding species and the proportion of protected areas. Furthermore, I found that the strength of the model (irrespective of the anuran breeding group) decreased after controlling for the wider unprotected matrix suggesting, at least for now, that amphibian species, in general, are maintaining viable populations within the wider unprotected matrix of the sub-continent. This study indicates that in addition to species with an aquatic tadpole stage, terrestrial-breeding anurans of the southern African sub-continent are in dire need of conservation action.

Keywords: Life history traits, anurans, southern African sub-continent, anthropogenic threats, land-use transformation, invasive alien plant species, human population density, biogeographical scale, areas where different frog breeding-groups occur, national scale, protected areas portfolio, species distributions.

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Disclaimer

This thesis consists of a series of chapters that have been prepared as stand-alone manuscripts for subsequent submission for publication purposes. Consequently, unavoidable overlaps and/or repetitions may occur between chapters.

Declaration

I, the undersigned hereby declare that the dissertation, which I hereby submit for the degree Master of Science (Zoology) at the University of Pretoria, is my own work and has not previously been submitted by me for a degree at this or any other tertiary institution.

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CHAPTER 1

General Introduction

The amphibian plight

Amphibians are currently the most-threatened (Stuart *et al.*, 2004; Mendelson *et al.*, 2006; IUCN, 2008), least-conserved (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2004) class of vertebrates, with population declines far exceeding those of other vertebrate groups. It has also been suggested that the current rate of extinction among amphibians is thought to be significantly higher compared to historical extinction rates (Houlahan *et al.*, 2000; McCallum, 2007; Wake & Vredenburg, 2008), and following McCallum (2007), this rate could even be as high as 25 000 to 40 000 times higher when the full suite of ‘imperiled’ amphibians is considered. This is mainly as a result of high numbers of amphibians considered as data deficient, although most of them could also be classified as highly threatened (Stuart *et al.*, 2004).

Only after the First World Congress of Herpetology in 1989 did scientists and conservation decision-makers realise, and acknowledge, the significant declines in amphibian populations, and the poor state of affairs concerning amphibian conservation on a global scale (Halliday, 1998; Houlahan *et al.*, 2000; Pounds *et al.*, 2006). Since then, considerable effort has gone into investigating the causes of these declines (Carey & Alexander, 2003; Collins & Storfer, 2003; Beebee & Griffiths, 2005). Habitat destruction (see Alford & Richards, 1999; Minter *et al.*, 2004; Cushman, 2006; Hof *et al.*, 2011) and biological invasions remain major threats to biodiversity, including amphibians (e.g., Drost & Fellers, 1996; Vredenburg, 2004; Angulo *et al.*, 2011; Li *et al.*, 2011). Other related threats include exploitation for human consumption and other related uses (Monheke *et al.*, 2011; Warkentin *et al.*, 2009), pollution and ultra-violet (U-V) radiation (Branch & Harrison, 2004; Beebee & Griffiths, 2005; Blackburn *et al.*, 2010).

Recently, more novel threats such as the chytrid fungus, *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* (*Bd*), have been implicated in several ‘mysterious’ population declines in the mid-Americas and Australia (e.g., Berger *et al.*, 1998; Pounds *et al.*, 2006; Skerratt *et al.*, 2007). Although *Bd* is now found on almost every continent (see James *et al.*, 2009), not all populations show the same susceptibility to this fungus. Amphibian populations within the African continent are a good example of such low susceptibility (Weldon *et al.*, 2004; Soto-Azat *et al.*, 2010; Bell *et al.*, 2011). In support of this, recent evidence (based on *Bd* surveys on the African continent) suggests that *Bd* is highly prevalent in Africa (Hopkins & Channing, 2003; Blackburn *et al.*, 2010; Kielgast *et al.*, 2010; Bell *et al.*, 2011; Conradie *et al.*, 2011) although it has not yet been linked with significant population declines. This, partially provides support for the proposition that *Bd* originated from the African continent (Weldon *et al.*, 2004; Weldon *et al.*, 2007; Soto-Azat *et al.*, 2010; however, see also James *et al.*, 2009).

Another conservation concern regarding the decline of amphibian populations relates to the issue that amphibians are not well-represented within the current conservation portfolio (e.g., Rodrigues *et al.*, 2004) and that declines often occur within protected areas (e.g., Drost & Fellers, 1996; Vredenburg, 2004;

Rachowicz *et al.*, 2006; Whitfield *et al.*, 2007). Efforts related to broad-scale conservation planning and reserve selection often fail to consider frogs in their assessments, and are instead biased towards vegetation types (Reyers *et al.*, 2001; Driver *et al.*, 2005; Reyers *et al.*, 2007). Amphibians represents a group with a high proportion of narrowly distributed endemics (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2004), thus reducing chances of being captured in the conservation portfolio, even when considering the conservative 10% (land under conservation level) as a bench-mark (Armstrong, 2001). These concerns are obviously not restricted to amphibians only. For example, recent studies suggested that, globally, protected areas are often not effective in capturing significant proportions of species, even in well-studied taxonomic groups such as mammals and birds (see Rodrigues *et al.*, 2004). There are implications related to the large amount of biodiversity found in the off-reserve matrix and how this contributes towards the overall conservation concern, namely population declines/species extinctions. This is especially of concern for amphibians given their small distribution and poor dispersal abilities (see Rodrigues *et al.*, 2004; D'Amen *et al.*, 2011). Seymour *et al.* (2001) reported that only about 35% of the amphibian species occurring in the southern African sub-region are found in protected areas.

Several reasons may explain why protected areas are not functioning as effectively as they should. It is argued that initially, reserve-selection and delineation was based on reasons other than their biological/ecological value (Lovejoy, 2006). Moreover, larger protected areas are mostly situated in areas of low primary productivity (Scott *et al.*, 2001; Araújo, 2003; Chown *et al.*, 2003; Reyers, 2004; Luck, 2007). To exacerbate the situation, some protected areas are also faced with the increasing problem of habitat destruction within their boundaries (see Liu *et al.*, 2001), fragmentation and isolation (de Fries *et al.*, 2005), leading to low habitat quality. In contrast, small protected areas are usually situated in highly productive land with high native floral richness (Richardson *et al.*, 2005; Luck 2007), but relatively small ecological process zones and surrounded by high human population densities (Parks & Harcourt, 2002; Chown *et al.*, 2003; 2007; Hansen & de Fries, 2007). As a result of this close proximity with highly human populated areas, land use change (Sinclair *et al.*, 2002; Chown *et al.*, 2003; Gaston, 2005) and invasive species encroachment (Lonsdale, 1999; Foxcroft & Richardson, 2003; Vredenburg, 2004; Clavero & Garcia-Berthou, 2005; Foxcroft *et al.*, 2007; Butchart, 2008; Clavero *et al.*, 2009; McGeoch *et al.*, 2010) continue to be the biggest threat to all biodiversity.

Critical considerations important for amphibian biodiversity and conservation assessments

Amphibians are a group with many biological adaptations, which consequently affects how each species utilises its environment, and in turn, the extent to which each species is being affected by anthropogenic activities (see Lips *et al.*, 2003; Bielby *et al.*, 2006; Becker *et al.*, 2007; see also Semlitsch *et al.*, 2009). This is highlighted by an array of different habitat types within which amphibians occur and breed (e.g., Schiøtz, 1999; Channing, 2001; du Preez & Carruthers, 2009). Subsequently, the incorporation of life history traits such as areas where different breeding groups occur, for example, is now being considered

more often by scientists when conducting conservation-related studies (Becker & Loyola, 2008; Loyola *et al.*, 2008; Becker *et al.*, 2010).

Building on previous work related to studies focusing on amphibian conservation and biogeography in southern Africa (Poynton, 1964; Drinkrow & Cherry, 1995; Poynton, 1999; Channing, 2001; Seymour *et al.*, 2001; Alexander *et al.*, 2004; du Preez & Carruthers, 2009), the present study focuses on the impacts of human activities on frogs at large spatial scales and the effectiveness of the protected area portfolio focusing specifically on species distributions, while also considering different biological traits (e.g., areas where different breeding habitat groups occur).

In this study (also following Channing, 2001 & Seymour *et al.*, 2001), southern Africa is defined as an area including South Africa, Lesotho, Swaziland, Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Zambia, Malawi and Angola (hereafter referred to as the southern African sub-continent; Figure 1). Amphibians in southern Africa are known for their diverse biological adaptations in as far as breeding habitats are concerned, and this diversity relates to an array of habitat types and the topography of the sub-region (Channing, 2001). In addition, amphibian diversity is relatively high in the sub-region, particularly at the family level, with no less than 15 of the 32 global anuran families represented (du Preez & Carruthers, 2009). Furthermore, amphibians play a critical role in the ecosystem in that they serve as an important link in the ecosystem as both predator and prey. Moreover, they serve as bio-indicators of both terrestrial and aquatic systems and they also help in controlling insect pest populations (Channing, 2001; du Preez & Carruthers, 2009).

Objectives and thesis structure

Based on 244 amphibian species from the southern African sub-continental in the datasets of the Southern African Frog Atlas Project (SAFAP; Minter *et al.*, 2004), Global Amphibian Assessment (IUCN, GAA; www.iucnredlist.org/initiatives/amphibians/) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF; www.gbif.org). Although most of the records included in the SAFAP dataset comprise of data collected a long time ago, with some records over 100 years old, data collected in the 8 years of the frog atlas period include 25 470 records as opposed to 16 975 collected before the atlas project began in 1995 (see Botts *et al.*, 2012). The SAFAP provided more spatial coverage as compared to frog data collected prior to SAFAP (Botts *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, this increased sampling intensity in the SAFAP dataset did not necessarily result in false range expansion as it is reported that as much as 60% of South African frogs have suffered range contractions in recent years (Botts *et al.*, 2012).

I examined, while considering different life history traits, the extent to which (i) amphibians are being affected by potential anthropogenic threats, and (ii) whether species distribution are being captured by protected areas. More specifically, in Chapter 2, I investigate the spatial relationship between areas where different frog breeding-groups occur and where elevated anthropogenic activities occurred, and the conservation implications thereof. Data on frog distribution for the southern African sub-continent were

used to identify biogeographical areas that are biologically meaningful within the sub-continent. A random draw technique was used to determine whether areas where different frog breeding-groups occur were characterized by higher levels of anthropogenic threats than expected by chance. This analysis was restricted to biogeographical areas within South Africa due to data limitations related to anthropogenic threats outside South Africa. Four measures (human population density, percentage land transformation, percentage protected area and invasive alien plants richness) expected to reflect threats were analysed.

In Chapter 3, I examine the extent to which the distribution of each species in question is represented by the current conservation portfolio. This relationship was examined at the southern African sub-continental scale, while considering different frog breeding-groups. In addition, I investigate the relationship between frog species richness and the proportion of protected land and how this relationship is affected by the exclusion of the wider unprotected matrix (i.e., focusing on protected areas only). Finally, Chapter 4 concludes the study with a general discussion of the major findings of the study, discusses future research direction, and provides recommendations.

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Figure 1. The spatial extent of the study area (southern African sub-continent as defined by Channing 2001 and Seymour *et al.*, 2001).

Chapter 2[†]

A biogeographical assessment of anthropogenic threats to areas where different frog breeding-groups occur in South Africa: implications for anuran conservation

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ABSTRACT

Aim

To determine the spatial relationship between areas where different frog breeding-groups occur and elevated anthropogenic activities, and the conservation implications thereof.

Location

South Africa.

Methods

Data on frog distribution for the southern African sub-continent were used to identify biogeographic areas within South Africa. A random draw technique was used to determine whether areas where different frog breeding-groups occur were characterised by higher levels of anthropogenic threats than expected by chance. Four measures (human population density, percentage land transformation, percentage protected area, and invasive alien plants richness) expected to reflect threats were analysed.

Results

Terrestrial-breeders were more often spatially associated with areas of threat than expected by chance in three of the seven biogeographical regions examined with land transformation and invasive alien plant richness being most significant. The south central was the only region where terrestrial-breeders were spatially congruent with protected areas. Areas where stream-breeders occur were spatially congruent with anthropogenic threats (with alien plants being most consistent) in five of the seven regions examined while protected areas were well represented in four of the seven regions. Non-significant results were found for permanent and temporary aquatic-breeders at both the national and the biogeographic scale.

Main conclusions

By analyzing data at the sub-continental scale we were able to identify regional threats to amphibians traditionally classified at species specific scales. Our study recognised land transformation and alien invasive plants as significant threats to areas important for the long-term breeding success of stream and terrestrial amphibians in South Africa. Areas where different breeding groups occur in the southwestern Cape showed the greatest spatial congruence with the threats examined. Areas where terrestrial breeding frogs occur are not well represented in the current conservation network. This has important implications in addressing the current status of threats on amphibians in a biogeographical context.

Keywords: anthropogenic threats, biogeographical scale, areas where different frog breeding-groups occur, national scale, protected areas network, South Africa.

INTRODUCTION

Based on recent assessments of population declines, amphibians represent the most threatened animal class globally (Stuart *et al.*, 2004; Mendelson *et al.*, 2006). It has been suggested that the size, growth and resource demands of the human population, ultimately leading to climate change, is the single most important reason for the recently observed changes in amphibian phenology, species range shifts, and an increase in rates of spread of infectious diseases (Vitousek *et al.*, 1997; Sala *et al.*, 2000; also see Hughes, 2000; Carey & Alexander, 2003; Pounds *et al.*, 2006). Other well-known threats also include land-use change, commercial over-exploitation, and the introduction of exotic species (Drost & Fellers, 1996; Blaustein & Kiesecker, 2002; Collins & Storfer, 2003; Beebee & Griffiths, 2005). An additional alarming aspect concerning amphibian conservation is that compared to other animal groups such as birds and mammals, it is only during the last two decades that scientists have become aware of the global extent and rate at which amphibians are declining (Halliday, 1998; Houlahan *et al.*, 2000, Pounds *et al.*, 2006). Although historical data from the 1970s indicated amphibian declines in several countries globally, scientists only acknowledged the magnitude of the amphibian problem at the First World Congress of Herpetology in 1989 (see Stuart *et al.*, 2004 and references therein).

In South Africa, the majority of conservation planning efforts conducted at the national scale have focused mainly on vegetation types (e.g., Reyers *et al.*, 2001; Driver *et al.*, 2005; Reyers *et al.*, 2007), birds (e.g., Bonn *et al.*, 2004; van Rensburg *et al.*, 2004a; Storch *et al.*, 2005), mammals (e.g., Andrews & O'Brien, 2000; Keith *et al.*, 2007), and to some extent, tortoises and terrapins (Branch *et al.*, 1995). However, limited studies have focused their attention on the anurans of the southern African sub-continent and their conservation. Previous studies by Poynton (1999), Seymour *et al.* (2001), and Alexander *et al.* (2004) have contributed significantly towards our understanding of anuran biogeographical patterns in southern Africa. In addition, Drinkrow & Cherry (1995) and Alexander *et al.* (2004) identified areas harbouring exceptional amphibian diversity as well as biologically important hotspots for South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland. Furthermore, using complementarity techniques, Seymour *et al.* (2001) identified areas important for frog conservation in the sub-continent. However, anuran diversity in southern Africa is relatively high, particularly at the family level, and with it the diversity in how each species utilises its environment. The incorporation of life history traits (e.g., areas where different frog breeding-groups occur) in stream-lining conservation efforts is currently gaining momentum (Becker & Loyola, 2008; Loyola *et al.*, 2008; Becker *et al.*, 2010). Conservation efforts neglecting to consider amphibian breeding habitat fall short of acknowledging that different life histories are affected differently by anthropogenic threats (Becker *et al.*, 2007).

South Africa holds a markedly rich anuran diversity with of 12 out of the 15 anuran families in sub-Saharan Africa represented in South Africa. For example, one small family of six ghost frog species (Heleophrynidae) is a near-endemic, forming a clade which has been placed basal to other Neobatrachia (Frost *et al.*, 2006). South Africa also has the largest radiation of pyxicephalid frogs (40 of 69 species) which display not only a wide range of body sizes from the tiny micro-frog (*Microbatrachella capensis*,

ca. 15 mm in body length) to the giant bullfrog (*Pyxicephalus adspersus*, ca. 245 mm), but also a range of reproductive modes including direct development, thought to have evolved at least twice within this group (van der Meijden *et al.*, 2011). Of the 118 frog species currently reported to occur in South Africa, 51 (43%) are endemics (Angulo *et al.*, 2011), and this figure is likely to increase (Channing *et al.*, 2011¹). South Africa also has remarkably good distribution records compared to other African countries. A frog atlas produced in 2004 (Minter *et al.*, 2004) provides distribution records for 117 species across southern Africa and these species have been recently up-dated for IUCN Red Listing (Measey, 2011).

In the present study, we assess the degree of spatial congruence between frog species representing different biological traits, focusing on areas where different breeding groups occur and elevated anthropogenic activities assuming that most of these activities potentially have negative impacts, either directly or indirectly, on the survival rates of frog populations. More specifically, we wanted to determine the spatial congruence of different frog breeding-groups with anthropogenic threats.

METHODS

Data

Given the high degree of variation in anthropogenic threats in geographic space, the effect of variation at the spatial scale was incorporated in our analyses. Consequently, spatial congruence between anthropogenic activities and areas where frog breeding-groups occur were assessed at two spatial scales as follows: 1) the whole of South Africa (hereafter referred to as the ‘national scale’); and 2) at smaller biogeographical areas representing different frog assemblages within South Africa.

Although our analyses were restricted to South Africa, mainly due to the restricted availability of data on anthropogenic activities in other southern African countries, the actual identification of biogeographical areas was based on anuran presence/absence data encompassing South Africa, Lesotho, Swaziland, Namibia, Botswana, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Zambia, Malawi and Angola (hereafter referred to as the southern African sub-continent). The identification of biogeographic areas based on data from the entire southern African sub-continent, thus excluding political boundaries, may allow for more biologically meaningful insights into anuran assemblages in South Africa. Data on frog distributions representing the southern African sub-continent were obtained from the South Africa frog atlas project (Minter *et al.*, 2004), Global Amphibian Assessment (IUCN, GAA 2008; www.iucnredlist.org/initiatives/amphibians/) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF; www.gbif.org).

Species occurrence records on the GBIF dataset are continuously up-dated by specialists and the general public as new occurrence records are reported. The accuracy of this dataset depends highly on correct species identification, and hence, the following data were excluded from our analysis: 1) all

¹ A new species of rain frog *Breviceps* has recently been discovered by A. Channing – Full citation: Channing A. (2012) A new species of rain frog from Namaqualand, South Africa (Anura: Brevicipitidae: *Breviceps*. *Zootaxa*, **3381**, 62–68.

unconfirmed or doubtful species occurrence records (i.e., occurrence of species outside their known range – using GAA polygons as ‘known range’); 2) species records based on fossil data because of the inconclusiveness of such data and also given that many of these species have become extinct; and 3) records that were not identified to the species level.

The identification of biogeographic areas was based on the latest authoritative amphibian taxonomic treatment by Frost *et al.*, (2006), based on occurrence records of 245 species at a quarter degree grid resolution. A hierarchical clustering technique was used to group these species based on similarities in their distributions (Legendre & Legendre, 1998; Seymour *et al.*, 2001; Alexander *et al.*, 2004; Chen & Bi, 2007). The aim was not to impose any clustering pattern on the distributional data by defining the number of clusters *a priori* (see Heikenheimo *et al.*, 2007), but rather to observe the naturally occurring structure of the data. We used Ward’s minimum variance (see Everitt, 1993) and Euclidian distance (Heikenheimo *et al.*, 2007) as the clustering and linkage methods, respectively (see also Gagné & Proulx, 2009; Heikenheimo *et al.*, 2009). Although hierarchical clustering is a well-established multivariate technique, its algorithm does not include testing for statistical significance (Everitt, 1993) such that decisions on the extent to which clusters differ from each other are subjective and/or based on prior knowledge. Consequently, the present study was based on optimisation methods (see Everitt, 1993) in an attempt to objectively identify biologically meaningful clusters within the generated southern African amphibian dataset.

It is inevitable for biogeographic areas to depict some degree of spatial overlap with each other, translating into pseudo-replication in subsequent analyses. Consequently, we used a systematic approach to reduce such overlaps, where two or more biogeographic areas overlap. Beta diversity measures highlight species compositional differences between focal and neighbouring cells (Williams, 1996; Williams *et al.*, 1999) and are thus commonly used to identify transitional areas between biogeographical regions (see van Rensburg *et al.*, 2004b and references therein). We used Simpson’s measure of beta diversity (hereafter referred to as β_{sim} -diversity) for this procedure (see Lennon *et al.*, 2001 and Koleff *et al.*, 2003 for more information on this diversity measure).

Areas with high β_{sim} -diversity values would, therefore, highlight areas with significant levels of species compositional differences when compared with neighbouring areas (van Rensburg *et al.*, 2004b). Thus, for each anuran biogeographical area that was identified for the greater southern African sub-continent, we identified grid cells showing spatial overlap with neighbouring biogeographical areas. Within each set of overlapping grid cells, a β_{sim} -diversity value was calculated for each grid cell (averaged across all pair-wise comparisons with adjacent cells) based on the frog species occurrence data. Overlapping cells with low (< 50%) β_{sim} -diversity values can, therefore, be treated as areas sharing a high level of species compositional similarities when compared between the given biogeographical areas. Hence, such areas would be less likely to represent the anuran assemblage of a specific biogeographical area and can thus be shared between biogeographical areas. In contrast, grid cells with high (> 50%) β_{sim} -diversity values can be regarded as areas sharing a low level of species compositional similarities and were, therefore, excluded from subsequent analyses in order to reduce pseudo-replication.

Eleven biogeographical areas were identified based on the anuran distribution data for the southern African sub-continent, with seven of these being represented in South Africa. Of significance is that these 11 biogeographical areas are similar to those previously identified by Poynton (1999), Seymour *et al.* (2001), and Alexander *et al.* (2004) despite being based on different data quality (the present study being based on the most recent available data), spatial scales and resolutions, and clustering approaches. Consequently, the naming of the biogeographical areas in the present study largely follows that of the studies cited above, and also with reference to the phytogeographic regions followed by Burgess *et al.* (2004) (see also Alexander *et al.*, 2004). Subsequent analyses at the biogeographical scale focused on the seven biogeographic areas represented in South Africa that included: 1) South-western Cape; 2) Southwest arid; 3) South central, 4) Maputaland; 5) East African lowlands; 6) South east lowland; and 7) Zambesian/Bushveld woodland assemblages (see Appendix S1 in “Supporting Information” for a map of biogeographic areas occurring in South Africa relative to the southern African sub-continent).

Analyses

To assess the degree of spatial congruence between areas where breeding groups occur and anthropogenic threats, we grouped all 117 frog species occurring in South Africa (du Preez & Carruthers, 2009; IUCN 2010; we did not include the monotypic *Cacosternum poyntoni* as we considered it to be a synonym of *C. nanum*) according to their developmental modes. These included 92 species of aquatic-breeders and 25 species of terrestrial-breeders (see Becker & Loyola, 2008; Loyola *et al.*, 2008). Aquatic-breeders were defined as species that require an aquatic stage to complete their life cycle and terrestrial-breeders as species that do not consist of an aquatic life stage to complete their life cycle. Depending on where the aquatic life stage occurs (see Becker *et al.*, 2010), eight species of the aquatic-breeders were further grouped into stream-breeders, 43 species into permanent aquatic-breeders, and 41 species into temporary aquatic-breeders. Using Arc View GIS 3.3 (ESRI, 1998), we mapped the spatial extent of areas where each of the four different breeding groups occur (i.e., terrestrial-, stream-, permanent aquatic-, and temporary aquatic-breeders) across South Africa based on the spatial distribution of each frog species representing a given category at the quarter-degree resolution (see Appendix S2 in “Supporting Information” for a map showing the spatial extent of areas where breeding groups occur).

To assess the degree of spatial congruence between anthropogenic threats and each of the areas where breeding groups occur, data on four potential anthropogenic threat variables were obtained for South Africa at the quarter-degree grid cell resolution (see Appendix S3 in “Supporting Information” for the distribution of potential anthropogenic threats considered). These anthropogenic threats included: 1) human population density based on a 2001 census data for South Africa (Anonymous, 2001); 2) percentage land transformation based on 1994–1995 data from Thompson (1996) and Fairbanks *et al.* (2000); 3) percentage protected area based on 637 national protected areas mapped in the World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA, 2004); and 4) alien plant species richness data. The alien plant species richness data were obtained from three sources, namely: 1) the *Southern African Plant Invaders Atlas* (“SAPIA”) with records for over 500 species (Henderson, 1998; 1999; 2001); 2) the National Herbarium

Pretoria Computerized Information Service (“PRECIS”) comprising over 800 000 herbarium specimens with records for over 24 000 taxa collated from all major South African herbaria (Germishuizen & Meyer, 2003); and 3) the “*Catalogue of Problem Plants in Southern Africa*” (Wells *et al.*, 1986) using a filtered list of taxa including 711 species alien to South Africa (for details, see Richardson *et al.*, 2003, pp. 295). It should be noted, however, that the available data only included woody invasive plant species, especially in natural and semi-natural ecosystems (Richardson *et al.*, 2005). We acknowledge that other factors such as infectious diseases, pollution and chemical contaminations are important threats to anurans (Branch & Harrison, 2004). These were, however, not included in our analyses because of the lack of appropriate data at the resolution and scale at which this study was conducted.

Co-linearity levels between the different potential anthropogenic threats were first determined prior to any statistical analysis (see Wilson *et al.*, 2008). To determine the co-linearity levels, the tolerance value for each predictor (i.e., anthropogenic threat) variable was determined. Tolerance is defined as 1 minus the squared multiple of a predictor variable with all other independent variables in the regression equation (StatSoft Inc., 2005). The lower the tolerance level of a given variable, the stronger the correlation between the variable in question and one or more of the other predictor variables. Following Quinn & Keough (2002), variables with tolerance values < 0.1 should be eliminated from subsequent analyses due to redundancy. None of the predictor variables were found to be redundant due to co-linearity (tolerance values ranged between 0.2 and 0.96). Human population density was found to be the strongest predictor of the other potential anthropogenic variables examined, except for percentage protected area which, in contrast, showed its strongest co-linearity with alien plants species richness.

To assess whether the grid cells representing areas where breeding groups occurs are likely to be characterized by higher human population density values than expected by chance, firstly, we calculated the mean human population density of the 1 147 grid cells representing terrestrial-breeders. The observed mean value was then compared with the mean human population density values found for 10 000 sets of randomly selected grid cells (selected from a pool of all possible grid cells, namely, 1 954 grid cells). The number of randomly selected grid cells was equivalent to the number of grid cells within which terrestrial-breeders are found (i.e., 1 147 grid cells; see van Rensburg *et al.*, 2004a where a similar approach was followed). Secondly, following van Rensburg *et al.* (2004a), mean human population density values were calculated for the remaining three groups of areas where frog breeding-groups occur (i.e., stream-, permanent aquatic-, and temporary aquatic-breeders). Thirdly, data for the remaining three potential anthropogenic threat (i.e., percentage land transformation, percentage protected area, and alien plant species richness) with reference to each of the areas where different breeding groups occur were similarly analysed as outlined above. Finally, mean values for each threat variable were compared between the different breeding habitat categories at the national scale, and across the different biogeographical areas using non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis analysis of variance (ANOVA; Zar, 1996). Where statistically significant differences were detected, maximally non-significant subsets ($P > 0.05$) were derived by the *a posteriori* Duncan’s *post-hoc* test procedure using ranked means (Sokal & Rohlf, 1981).

RESULTS

Although areas representing terrestrial- and stream-breeders show a strong association with protected areas at the national scale (Tables 1 & 2), these areas had significantly larger mean human population density, land transformation and alien plant richness values ($P < 0.001$; 10,000 permutations) than expected by chance (Table 1). In contrast, all these anthropogenic variables scored their lowest mean values in areas representing both permanent aquatic- and temporary aquatic-breeders (Table 2), and spatially, these areas (representing aquatic-breeders) showed no significant congruence with any of the threat variables (Table 1).

Considering the biogeographical scale, terrestrial-breeders were spatially congruent with anthropogenic threats than expected by chance in three of the seven biogeographical regions examined, namely the south central, the southwest arid, and the southwestern Cape regions (Table 1). Land transformation and alien plant richness were most significant in these regions. Moreover, the south central was the only region where terrestrial-breeders showed significant spatial congruence with protected areas (Table 1). In contrast, stream-breeders showed significant anthropogenic threats in five of the seven biogeographical regions examined, the most notable results being: 1) the consistent significant threat posed by alien plant species richness (in four of the five regions), and 2) the overall strong association with protected areas, although a significant negative association was true for the Maputaland region (Table 1). No statistically significant results were found for permanent aquatic- and temporary aquatic-breeders (Table 1). Compared to all the biogeographical regions examined, the east African lowlands was the only region where none of the threats were spatially congruent with any of the areas where frog breeding-groups occur (Table 1).

Comparing mean values for each threat variable across all the biogeographical areas representing different frog assemblages, the southwestern Cape together with Maputaland region showed significantly higher mean human population density, land transformation and alien plant species richness compared to the other regions examined (Table 3). The south central followed by the south east lowlands and the Maputaland are the least protected regions; while the Zambesian/Bushveld woodlands followed by east African lowlands were highly congruent with the percentage of protected area (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

The distribution of stream- and terrestrial-breeding frog species in South Africa, at both the national and biogeographical scales, were spatially congruent with anthropogenic activities that are likely to threaten their existence. Of concern is that most of the threatened stream-breeders in South Africa are from a single near-endemic family, the Heleophrynidae (which also occurs in Lesotho and Swaziland). Heleophrynidae tadpoles are especially vulnerable to factors affecting water flow and quality such as alien invasive plants

(see further discussion below) because of their long period (> one year) to complete metamorphosis and thus requires permanent streams (du Preez & Carruthers, 2009).

At the national scale, the present study suggests that terrestrial- and stream-breeders are well-represented by the current protected area network in South Africa. These results support Drinkrow & Cherry (1995) who found that *ca.* 90% of anuran species in South Africa were also congruent with protected areas. However, careful consideration of factors that may negate the significance of these positive results is warranted. Firstly, although a given species is present in one or more protected areas, the extent to which its full distributional range is being represented (or not) by a matrix of protected areas is often unknown. This is because the presence of a given species within a protected area does not guarantee long-term protection of viable populations of the species (Armstrong, 2001). Secondly, should the sampling of frog atlas data be biased towards protected areas, spurious results may be obtained when examining spatial patterns between frog diversity and protected areas (Botts *et al.*, 2011). Thirdly, at the biogeographic scale, both stream- and especially terrestrial-breeders were poorly represented in the reserve network within most of the biogeographic regions (see further discussion below). Fourthly, the current analysis was undertaken at a QDS resolution, which covers a much larger area than frog breeding habitats. Several studies have highlighted positive relationship between human induced threats and biodiversity at such coarse spatial scales (Chown *et al.*, 2003; Pautasso, 2007). We do acknowledge that negative relationship might be true at more local level investigations. Finally, the potential influence of a combination of the above factors also needs to be taken into consideration.

Our non-significant results for both permanent and temporary aquatic-breeders compliment Darwall *et al.* (2009) who also highlighted the paucity of protected areas within freshwater systems (see also Nel *et al.*, 2007). Based on a global dataset, Becker & Loyola (2008) found that aquatic-breeders have an exceptionally high extinction risk due to their generally low congruence with protected areas. It is possible that the general lack of spatial congruency with protected areas globally, especially for amphibians (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2004; Sodhi *et al.*, 2008) may contribute towards high extinction risk. This may be due to limited options to build more comprehensive conservation networks, especially in areas important for conservation because of the positive relationship between species richness and human densities (or impacts) as has been shown for many countries globally (Chown *et al.*, 2003; Gaston, 2005; Hugo & van Rensburg 2008; Luck *et al.*, 2010). An additional explanation for poor reserve representation that may especially be true for stream-breeders where individuals generally have small distribution, is that conservation decisions may often be implemented at a scale simply too coarse to capture fine-scale heterogeneity in species distributions (Rebelo, 1997; Reyers *et al.*, 2001; Cowling & Pressey, 2003; Reyers, 2004).

Given that none of the threats examined in this study showed significant spatial congruence with both permanent and temporary aquatic-breeders at both the national and biogeographic scales, it may be possible that the threats used in our analysis were not sensitive enough to be applied in the analysis of aquatic systems despite some significant relationships between stream-breeders and some threats used

herein. It may be possible that other threats such as water pollution, chemical contamination as well as the chytrid fungus (*Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis*) may have more influence on the survival of aquatic-breeding populations locally (Blaustein & Kiesecker, 2002; Collins & Storfer, 2003; see also Kerby *et al.* (2010) on why amphibians may be poor environmental indicators). Although there is a need for further research, the presence of the chytrid fungus has been confirmed in some aquatic-breeders in South Africa (Hopkins & Channing, 2003; Weldon *et al.*, 2004), despite having not resulted in any known mass frog die-offs.

Other potential explanations for the low spatial congruence between aquatic species distributions and anthropogenic threats (including protected area distribution) may include factors such as: 1) spatially, the aquatic-breeders are found in almost every grid cell spanning the study area (see Measey, 1998; Lobos & Measey, 2002; Lobos & Jaksic, 2005; Tolley *et al.*, 2010 for more information on the distribution, invasion patterns and adaptability of these species), thus there is a high likelihood for these species to maintain viable populations in areas that are not yet highly threatened and/or under any formal protection (see Appendix S2, B & C); and 2) given the large spatial range of the species within these breeding groups, there is a low likelihood that a given mean threat value calculated across the grid cells representing the observed spatial range (for a given breeding group) will show a significantly higher (or lower) value compared to the randomly selected means due to the large spatial overlap between the grid cells representing the observed *versus* those representing a randomly selected mean. More detailed studies of anthropogenic threats to aquatic breeders at the regional scale are therefore needed.

There is poor spatial overlap between protected areas and areas where different frog breeding-groups occur at the biogeographical scale. Compared to the other breeding groups, stream-breeders were the best represented group within the current reserve network although significance was only reached in the south east lowlands, southwestern arid and southwestern Cape biogeographic areas. These results may be explained by the way protected areas were historically designated in South Africa such as the bias towards the savanna and the fynbos biomes (Reyers *et al.*, 2001) with an emphasis for conserving riparian zones, high altitude sites and forested habitat types (Rebello, 1997). A conservation bias towards riparian zones may contribute positively to the conservation of frog species in general. However, riparian zones in South Africa (le Maitre *et al.*, 2000; van Wilgen *et al.*, 2001; Meek *et al.*, 2010) and elsewhere (Greenwood *et al.*, 2004) are among the most heavily invaded habitat types (mainly by plants) and this is also true in protected areas (Foxcroft & Richardson, 2003; Foxcroft *et al.*, 2007). Our analyses support the findings that alien plant species richness was the most prominent threat to stream-breeders across the different biogeographic areas.

Biological invasions in general are known to have dire consequences for anurans. In South Africa, compared to global trends, biological invasions (mainly due to invasive alien plants species) affect a disproportionate number of threatened anuran species (37% compared to 16% globally; Angulo *et al.*, 2011). For example, Branch & Harrison (2004) reported that exotic pine stands have negative outcomes on the recruitment rates of Hewitt's ghost frog (*Heleophryne hewitti*) due to a reduction in stream flow. The

impacts of spreading invasive alien vegetation and afforestation is also well-known for affecting amphibians in fire-driven biomes such as the fynbos due to increased fuel and therefore fire intensity from which many threatened amphibians struggle to recover (Minter *et al.*, 2004; Angulo *et al.*, 2011). This was supported by our analyses where alien plant species richness was prominent in the southwestern Cape for both terrestrial- and stream-breeders. Alien plant species may also lead to a reduction in both the number and abundance of native insect species which support indigenous amphibian biota (Maerz *et al.*, 2005). Data on invading amphibians in South Africa is however lacking (van Wilgen *et al.*, 2008). Nonetheless, there have been reports of human-mediated range expansion of the painted reed frog (*Hyperolius marmoratus*) in the western Cape province of South Africa (Tolley *et al.*, 2008), and the introduction of the Guttural Toad (*Amietophrynus gutturalis*) in sub-urban Cape Town (de Villiers, 2006), which has begun to rapidly expand in recent years (Measey & Davies, 2011).

Land transformation and alien plant richness seem to be the most dominant threats to terrestrial-breeders with significant results found in the south central, the southwest arid, and the southwestern Cape regions (Angulo *et al.*, 2011; Table 1). The grassland biome represents one of the most highly populated and highly transformed parts of South Africa. This biome has a number of densely populated centres mainly due to employment opportunities in the mining and agricultural industries (O'Connor & Bredenkamp, 1997; Bredenkamp *et al.*, 2006) which may elevate the vulnerability of terrestrial-breeders. However, significant spatial overlap between areas where terrestrial breeders occur and the proportion of protected areas was only found in the south central region, despite only 2% of this region being under formal protection. O'Connor & Bredenkamp (1997) found that a high proportion of plant species (*ca.* 78%) were congruent with protected areas within the grassland biome (which spans the bulk of the south central biogeographic area), despite low levels of protection in this biome. Of significance for amphibians in these areas is that most of the terrestrial-breeders are brevipeptids. Some of these species occur only in the low-lying and highly transformed areas of the Western Cape Province (Minter, 2004). Conversely, members of the other terrestrial-breeding genus *Arthroleptella* (Pyxicephalidae) occur mostly in high altitude protected sites of the Western Cape Province (Channing, 2004).

In conclusion, both globally and in South Africa, Red List assessments have highlighted the consistency between patterns of major threats affecting amphibian conservation; most notably agricultural and aqua-cultural activities, and in South Africa, these are coupled with biological invasions (Angulo *et al.*, 2011). In a recent global assessment, compared to birds and mammals, the extinction risk of amphibians showed the greatest increase over time because of biological invasions (McGeoch *et al.*, 2010). Using all species at a sub-continental scale (at a QDS resolution), rather than a single species approach used by Red List Assessors, our study identified land transformation and alien invasive plants as significant threats to areas important for the long-term breeding success of both stream- and terrestrial-breeders in South Africa. At the biogeographical scale, the areas where different frog breeding-groups occur in the southwestern Cape showed the greatest spatial congruence with the threats examined, especially alien invasive plants. Finally, our study suggests that areas where different frog breeding-groups occur are, in general, not well-represented in the current conservation network when examined at the

biogeographical scale and this was true especially for terrestrial-breeders. In areas where a breeding group was reasonably well-represented in the protected area network (mainly stream-breeders), there is a need for further research to investigate the extent to which frog species distributional ranges are being captured by the reserve network in order to assess long-term population viability. This is an important, but currently outstanding quantification that needs attention to further our efforts in amphibian conservation. The results presented here have important implications in addressing the current status of threats on amphibians in a biogeographical context, which to date has largely been anecdotal (see Minter *et al.*, 2004).

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Table 1. Results indicating whether grid cells in South Africa representing different groups of frogs, based on where each group occur, have significantly greater values of anthropogenic threats than expected by chance based on 10 000 permutations. The assessment was based on two spatial scales, namely, a national scale and a smaller biogeographical scale (consisting of seven biogeographical areas (see the Methods section on how these areas were identified)). 1 = Human population density; 2 = Percentage land transformation; 3 = Alien plant species richness; and 4 = Percentage protected area.

Region	Areas where different breeding habitats occur			
	Terrestrial	Stream	Permanent aquatic	Temporary aquatic
National	(1-4) ⁺⁺⁺	(1-4) ⁺⁺⁺	NS	NS
South central	(1,2) ⁺⁺⁺ (3,4) ⁺⁺	NS	NS	NS
Zambesian/ Bushveld woodlands	NS	3 ⁺⁺ (2,4) ⁺	NS	NS
East African lowlands	NS	NS	NS	NS
Southeast lowlands	NS	3 ⁺⁺⁺ 4 ⁺⁺	NS	NS
Maputaland	NS	4 ⁻⁻⁻	NS	NS
Southwest arid	2 ⁺⁺ 3 ⁺	4 ⁺⁺⁺ 3 ⁺⁺	NS	NS
Southwestern Cape	3 ⁺	4 ⁺⁺⁺ 3 ⁺⁺ 2 ⁻⁻⁻	NS	NS

Statistical significance higher than expected by chance: ⁺⁺⁺ = $P < 0.001$; ⁺⁺ = $P < 0.01$; ⁺ = $P < 0.025$; statistical significance lower than expected by chance: ⁻⁻⁻ = $P > 0.001$; NS = not statistically significant.

Table 2. Kruskal-Wallis analysis of variance (ANOVA) test of anthropogenic threat variables in areas where each frog breeding-group occur identified in South Africa at the national scale.

Areas where different frog breeding-groups occur	Anthropogenic threats			
	Human population density (2001)	Percentage land transformation	Alien plants species richness	Percentage protected area
	Mean ± S.E			
	$H_{(1,3)} = 278.2;$	$H_{(1,3)} = 187.4;$	$H_{(1,3)} = 264.5;$	$H_{(1,3)} = 141.7;$
	$P < 0.001$	$P < 0.001$	$P < 0.001$	$P < 0.001$
Permanent aquatic	22,932 ± 2,028.2 ^a	21 ± 0.6 ^a	17 ± 0.6 ^a	6 ± 0.4 ^a
Temporary aquatic	22,982 ± 2,033.3 ^a	21 ± 0.6 ^a	17 ± 0.6 ^a	6 ± 0.4 ^a
Terrestrial	35,439 ± 3391.9 ^b	28 ± 0.8 ^b	22 ± 0.9 ^b	9 ± 0.6 ^b
Stream	46,117 ± 6,371.5 ^c	35 ± 1.5 ^c	36 ± 2.0 ^c	11 ± 1.1 ^c

S.E. = Standard Error; superscripts denote the significantly different subsets based on Duncan's *post hoc* test procedure

Table 3. Kruskal-Wallis analysis of variance (ANOVA) test of anthropogenic threat variables and biogeographical regions representing different anuran assemblages in South Africa.

Biogeographic region	Anthropogenic threats			
	Human population density (2001)	Percentage land transformation	Alien plants species richness	Percentage protected area
	Mean ± S.E			
	$H_{(1,6)} = 416.0;$ $P < 0.001$	$H_{(1,6)} = 536.3;$ $P < 0.001$	$H_{(1,6)} = 468.0;$ $P < 0.001$	$H_{(1,6)} = 425.1;$ $P < 0.001$
South central	19,929 ± 3,609.6 ^a	15 ± 0.8 ^a	12 ± 0.7 ^a	2 ± 0.3 ^a
Zambesian/ Bushveld woodlands	35,579 ± 4,671.9 ^b	24 ± 1.4 ^b	22 ± 2.0 ^b	18 ± 1.8 ^b
East African lowlands	23,895 ± 4,139.9 ^b	36 ± 5.0 ^{b,c}	26 ± 3.4 ^{b,c}	16 ± 3.0 ^b
South east lowlands	22,674 ± 3,125.3 ^b	26 ± 1.3 ^c	23 ± 1.3 ^c	4 ± 0.5 ^c
Maputaland	86,090 ± 20,887.0 ^c	45 ± 2.8 ^c	42 ± 4.2 ^c	7 ± 1.3 ^{c,d}
Southwest arid	7,514 ± 3,971.5 ^d	6 ± 0.8 ^a	12 ± 1.1 ^a	11 ± 1.3 ^d
Southwestern Cape	55,812 ± 14,035.8 ^{b,c}	59 ± 2.0 ^c	51 ± 3.2 ^c	14 ± 1.3 ^b

S.E. = Standard Error; superscripts denote the significantly different subsets based on Duncan's *post hoc* test procedure.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Appendix S1. A quarter-degree grid cell map of seven anuran biogeographic regions occurring within the political boundaries of South Africa.

Appendix S2. Maps indicating the spatial distribution of anuran species richness based on four (A to D) areas where different frog breeding-groups occur in South Africa. A = stream breeding species, B = permanent aquatic breeding species, C = temporary aquatic breeding species, D = terrestrial breeding species.

Appendix S3. Maps showing the extent of the distribution of proposed anuran threats (A to D) in South Africa. A = human population density, B = land use transformation, C = alien plants species richness, D = percentage protected area.

CHAPTER 3*

The ecological effectiveness of protected areas portfolio on amphibian biodiversity: a southern African perspective

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ABSTRACT

Amphibians represent the most-threatened and least-conserved animal group globally. Investigating the amphibian fauna of the southern African sub-continent, we assessed the relationship between amphibian species richness and the proportion of protected areas per grid cell, before and after controlling for the wider unprotected matrix, spatial autocorrelation and environmental correlates. We found that the current conservation portfolio does not include amphibian diversity adequately. A negative relationship was found between species richness of terrestrial breeding frogs and the proportion of protected areas per grid cell. This relationship persisted after controlling for spatial autocorrelation. A positive relationship was found between permanent- and temporary aquatic-breeding species only for “both protected and unprotected areas models”. We predominantly found a non-significant relationship between the richness of stream-breeding species and the proportion of protected areas, before and after controlling for spatial autocorrelation. The model strength decreased for all species groups after controlling for the wider unprotected matrix suggesting that, at least for now, amphibian species, in general, are maintaining viable populations within the wider unprotected areas of the southern African sub-continent. Although these results suggest that protected areas of the sub-continent are not doing that well in capturing anuran biodiversity, efforts are needed to investigate the role of small protected areas in conserving frog biodiversity in the long-term.

Keywords: life history traits, amphibians, protected areas portfolio, southern African sub-continent, species distributions.

INTRODUCTION

Conservation biologists are continually confronted with questions related to the most effective ways to conserve the largest possible proportion of biodiversity while minimising potential conflicts with other land use activities (Marris, 2007). Protected areas, at least in part, contribute towards addressing questions related to effective conservation strategies as they often provide refuge to many forms of biodiversity and are thus central to current conservation initiatives (Margules & Pressey, 2000; Lovejoy 2006; see also Tang *et al.*, 2011). However, not all species occur within protected areas (Caro, 2001; Blann, 2006). For most countries, options are often limited for expanding on their current reserve portfolios to generate a more comprehensive one, which protects all species and significantly reduces conflict with human activities by designating new reserves in areas with lower human populations (Chown *et al.*, 2003; Luck, 2007). Given these limitations, it is therefore ideal for those species that are represented in protected areas to have a large enough proportion of their population present in such areas in order for them to maintain viable populations in time and space (Margules & Pressey 2000; Pressey *et al.*, 2007).

Empirical studies however, suggest that globally, conservation areas are not effective in capturing significant proportions of species, even in well-studied taxonomic groups (mammals and birds), let alone less-studied groups such as amphibians and reptiles (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2004; D'Amen *et al.*, 2011). This is despite earlier conservation efforts to establish protected areas in regions rich in mammalian diversity (see Siegfried, 1987; Rebelo, 1997; Greve *et al.*, 2008; 2011), and a global increase in the number of proclaimed protected areas in the last 40 years (Ervin, 2003).

Apart from reserve limitations leading to inadequacies in species and population representivity and persistence, there are a myriad of threats currently facing protected areas worldwide, leading to some reserves being less efficient in conserving biodiversity (Margules & Pressey, 2000; Liu *et al.*, 2001; see also Evans *et al.*, 2006a; Jackson *et al.* 2009b). Globally, most large protected areas are situated in areas of low primary productivity, an important explanatory variable for species richness patterns (Siegfried, 1987; Reyers, 2004; Luck, 2007), with the opposite being true for small protected areas. Smaller protected areas are often surrounded by higher human population densities (Parks & Harcourt, 2002; Chown *et al.*, 2003; Luck *et al.*, 2007; see also Wittemyer *et al.*, 2008). Protected areas also need to overcome the immediate threat posed by biological invasions leading to habitat loss (see Foxcroft & Richardson, 2003; Foxcroft *et al.*, 2007). For example, in South Africa, Richardson *et al.* (2005) found that species rich areas, which often correlate positively with reserve size (Evans *et al.*, 2006a; Jackson *et al.*, 2009a, b, Greve *et al.*, 2011), were also rich in alien plant diversity (see also Stholgrens *et al.*, 1999). Finally, given current and predicted species range shifts as a result of large-scale changing climates (Pounds *et al.*, 1999;

D'Amen *et al.*, 2011; Minter, 2011), species conservation within the off-reserve matrix in addition to existing protected areas is needed (see Evans *et al.*, 2006; Lovejoy, 2006; Hansen & de Fries, 2007; Gallo *et al.*, 2009; Jackson *et al.*, 2009; O' Connor & Kuyler, 2009).

Amphibians are a good example of a vertebrate group experiencing significant conservation challenges due to some of the protected area limitations and threats mentioned above. Indeed, globally, amphibians represent the most at-risk (Stuart *et al.*, 2004; Mendelson *et al.*, 2006) and least-conserved vertebrate group (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2004). There are several reasons (either independent or in combination) that might explain why amphibians in general are poorly conserved. First, the characteristically high proportion of range-restricted endemic species within this animal group reduces the chances of such species being captured within conservation areas. Second, diseases and climate change, being factors that will affect populations both within and outside protected areas, contribute towards the general threat that amphibians face in addition to not being adequately conserved (Stuart *et al.*, 2004; Pounds *et al.*, 2006; Wake & Vredenburg, 2008; Whitfield *et al.*, 2008). Third, biological invasions are a major threat to biodiversity both within and outside protected areas, and are known to have dire consequences for anurans (Drost & Fellers, 1996; see also Vredenburg, 2004; Li *et al.*, 2011; Martin & Murray, 2011). In South Africa, compared to global trends, biological invasions (mainly due to invasive alien plants species) affect a significantly high number of threatened anuran species (37% compared to 16% globally; Angulo *et al.*, 2011). Fourth, efforts related to broad scale conservation planning and reserve selection often fail to consider frogs in their assessments, and are instead biased towards either well-studied taxa such as mammals (Andrews & O'Brien, 2000; Keith *et al.*, 2007), birds (Bonn *et al.*, 2004; van Rensburg *et al.*, 2004; Storch *et al.*, 2005; Evans *et al.*, 2006; Greve *et al.*, 2011) or land type classes (Reyers *et al.*, 2001; Driver *et al.*, 2005; Reyers *et al.*, 2007). Fifth, amphibians represent an ectothermic vertebrate group whose habitat (and hence conservation) requirements are at best, poorly known (Buckley & Jetz, 2007). Most importantly, the recent availability of amphibian species distribution (Global Amphibian Assessment) allows for investigatory analyses into the coverage of protected areas (IUCN, GAA; www.iucnredlist.org/initiatives/amphibians/).

In southern Africa, anuran diversity is relatively high, particularly at the family level, and with it the diversity in how each species utilises its environment. The incorporation of life history traits (e.g., areas where different breeding habitat groups occur) in stream-lining conservation efforts is currently gaining momentum (Becker & Loyola, 2008; Loyola *et al.*, 2008; Becker *et al.*, 2010; see also Hero *et al.*, 2005). Thus, conservation efforts neglecting to consider amphibian breeding habitat fall short of acknowledging that different life histories are affected differently by anthropogenic threats (Becker *et al.*, 2007). The aim of this study was to assess the ecological effectiveness of

protected areas in conserving amphibian biodiversity. Following Becker *et al.* (2007), we focused our attention on areas where different amphibian breeding groups occur (life history traits). This is of critical importance to amphibians given the heavy reliance of current conservation efforts on the protected areas (Gaston *et al.*, 2006) and that habitat destruction remains the most pervasive threat to biodiversity (e.g. Cushman, 2006; Hof *et al.*, 2011). More specifically, the aims of this analysis were: i) to examine how well the current conservation portfolio represent anuran diversity (species geographic range representation), ii) to assess the relationship between frog species richness and the proportion of protected land per grid cell; and iii) to investigate how this relationship is affected by the exclusion of the wider unprotected matrix (i.e., focusing only on areas represented by protected areas, i.e., the ‘PA-only model’). We do acknowledge substituting space for time is not ideal, but given the limitations in the availability of data collected at different time intervals, this method provides a measure of how well protected areas are conserving biodiversity (see Chown 2010). More importantly, all our analyses are undertaken with special reference to both spatial autocorrelation and environmental factors such as primary productivity, soil type, and elevation that are known to influence broad-scale species distribution patterns (Evans *et al.*, 2006, Zhao *et al.*, 2006; Buckley & Jetz, 2007; Qian *et al.*, 2007; Kallimanis *et al.*, 2008).

METHODS

Data

Species distribution data for southern African frogs were obtained from the Southern Africa Frog Atlas Project (SAFAP; Minter *et al.*, 2004), Global Amphibian Assessment (IUCN, GAA; www.iucnredlist.org/initiatives/amphibians/) and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF; www.gbif.org) datasets. Species occurrence records from the GBIF dataset are continuously up-dated by specialists and the general public, as new occurrence records are reported. The accuracy of this dataset depends highly on correct species identification, and hence, the following data were excluded from our analysis: i) all unconfirmed or doubtful species occurrence records (i.e., occurrence of species outside their ‘known range’– using GAA polygons as ‘known range’); ii) species records based on fossil data because of the inconclusiveness of such data and also given that many of these species have become extinct; and iii) records that were not identified to species level. Frog species occurring within the southern African sub-continent encompassing Angola, Botswana, Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, South Africa, Swaziland, Zambia and Zimbabwe were considered (Channing, 2001; Seymour *et al.*, 2001). The classification of species was based on the latest authoritative amphibian taxonomic treatment by Frost *et al.* (2006). To this end, our analysis included

244 frog species occurring within the southern African sub-continent at the quarter-degree grid cell (QDGC) resolution representing 8 551 grid cells.

Following Becker & Loyola (2008) and Loyola *et al.* (2008), species were grouped according to differences in their developmental modes (i.e., whether they develop directly or have a tadpole stage and subsequently to areas where a particular species breed). This information was obtained from different sources (e.g., Schiøtz, 1999; Channing, 2001; du Preez & Carruthers, 2009). Where information on the type of habitat where a particular frog species breeds was unknown, the species was placed in the same category as the members of the same genus (wherever this was found to be consistent). In cases where this was inconsistent, the species was omitted altogether (e.g., *Hyperolius gularis* and *Hyperolius vilhenai*). Furthermore, species only known from single records (e.g., *Aubria masako*, *Cacosternum poyntoni* and *Hylarana darlingi*) and for which no recent collection records were available were also omitted from subsequent analysis. Our final grouped data consisted of 239 frog species of which 203 species were classed as aquatic- and 36 species as terrestrial-breeding species. The 203 aquatic-breeding species were further divided into sub-groups associated with where their aquatic life stages occur. Consequently, 12 species were grouped as stream-breeders, 114 species as permanent aquatic-breeders, and 77 species as temporary aquatic-breeders (see Appendix 1 for species-specific distribution information).

Data on the proportion of protected land for the southern African sub-continent were obtained from World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA, 2009). Subsequently, the proportion of the grid cell that constitutes protected land was calculated for all the grid cells that were spatially congruent with protected areas and was expressed as a percentage. In total, protected areas were present in 2 909 (34.2%) quarter degree grid cells covering the study area. Species richness patterns are a function of many factors other than simply the size of the available area (Seymour *et al.*, 2001; van Rensburg *et al.*, 2002, Chown *et al.*, 2003; Evans *et al.*, 2006a, b; Kallimanis *et al.*, 2008; Jackson *et al.*, 2008; 2009a). For this reason, we considered other environmental variables known to influence species richness patterns at broad spatial scales.

These environmental factors included; i) primary productivity; ii) soil type diversity; iii) and mean range of elevation. Primary productivity is strongly correlated with normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI), known to be an important explanatory variable for spatial variation in biodiversity patterns in South Africa (O'Brien, 1993; 1998; O'Brien *et al.*, 1998 for plants; van Rensburg *et al.*, 2002, Chown *et al.*, 2003; Evans *et al.*, 2006b; 2006a for birds; Evans *et al.*, 2006a for frogs; see Evans *et al.*, 2005 for a review). We used mean annual net primary productivity values, averaged between 1981 and 2000, obtained from the global land cover facility (GLCF), University of Maryland (www.glcapp.glcfc.umd.edu:8080/esdi/index.jsp). Soil type diversity and elevation range

are typically used as surrogates for habitat heterogeneity (Seymour *et al.*, 2001; Zhao *et al.*, 2006; Qian *et al.*, 2007; Kallimanis *et al.*, 2008) and are known to influence patterns of amphibian distribution in the southern African sub-continent (Seymour *et al.*, 2001). We used the harmonised soil type diversity map for Africa obtained from the African water resources database (www.fao.org/geonetwork). Elevation range was accounted for as the maximum minus the minimum elevation on the 2.5 arc minutes resolution making up a QDGC (Zhao *et al.*, 2006; Qian *et al.*, 2007) and was obtained from Digital Elevation Model (DEM; www.worldclim.org/).

Analyses

Following Wilson *et al.* (2008), the tolerance value of each environmental variable was used to first calculate co-linearity levels between the different variables prior to any statistical analysis. Tolerance is defined as 1 minus the squared multiple of a predictor variable with all other independent variables in the regression equation (StatSoft Inc., 2005). The lower the tolerance level of a given variable, the stronger the correlation between the variable in question and one or more of the other predictor variables (Quinn & Keough, 2002; see also Wilson *et al.*, 2008). Variables with tolerance values less than 0.1 should be eliminated from subsequent analyses due to redundancy (Quinn & Keough, 2002). None of the predictor variables were found to be redundant due to co-linearity (tolerance values ranged between 0.93 and 0.99) and were therefore included in subsequent analyses. Appropriate data transformation procedures were employed in order to normalise the data. Where appropriate, species richness was square-root transformed and the proportion of protected land per grid cell, net primary productivity, soil type diversity and range of elevation were all logarithmically transformed to base 10 following Evans *et al.* (2006).

Statistically, when comparing models using data both with and without grid cells that lacked protected land, the former (i.e., models including both protected and unprotected areas) will contain more data points (and hence, degrees of freedom) and might therefore inherently result in a better fit of the data compared to those models constructed for protected area cells only (see Evans *et al.*, 2006b). For instance, considering both protected and unprotected cells, terrestrial-breeding species were represented in 6 294 cells while only 2 568 of these cells contained protected areas. To account for this bias, using terrestrial-breeders as an example, we randomly sampled 2 568 data points from a pool of all possible 6 294 grid cells representing terrestrial-breeders. Each data point represented a mean value, averaged over 1 000 random samples selected from all possible values representing terrestrial-breeders. These data points were then used in all subsequent analyses to assess the relationship between the proportion of protected area per grid cell (including both protected and

unprotected grid cells) and species richness in terrestrial frog breeders. A similar approach was followed for all other breeding groups.

For each frog breeding-group, univariate tests were used to assess the relationships between the proportion of protected area per grid cell, both with and without grid cells that lacked protected land, respectively, and frog species richness. In order to compare parameter estimates between models that used data with grid cells that lacked protected land and those without, we assessed if there was overlap in their 84% confidence intervals; a lack of overlap in such confidence intervals indicates that parameter estimates differ significantly from each other with $P < 0.05$ (Payton *et al.*, 2003, see also Evans *et al.*, 2006b; Hugo & van Rensburg, 2008, where a similar approach was followed). It is reported that the use of 95% confidence intervals actually results in the adoption of a significance threshold much lower than 0.05 (approximately at 0.01) and hence the use of a less conservative 84% confidence interval.

Relationships between the species richness of different frog breeding-groups and the proportion of protected areas per grid cell were assessed further using multiple regression models, with net primary productivity (NPP), proportion of protected land per grid cell (PPA), soil type and elevation range as predictors. We did not set out to determine the strength of the interaction term between proportion of protected areas per grid cell and primary productivity. This is because exploratory analyses found this interaction term not to be significant in explaining richness patterns and it was also found only to be significant in non-spatial models explaining species richness patterns in birds (see Evans *et al.*, 2006a). We implemented an information theoretical approach to model selection by conducting multiple regression models based on all possible combinations of our predictor variables. We then used Akaike's Information Criteria (AIC) to determine the best possible models, given the data using Akaike weights (w_i) (Burnham & Anderson, 2001; Johnson & Omland, 2004). These values (w_i) were only reported for the multivariate models (see Table 3) as for univariate models, the values were too small and thus insignificant.

For both the univariate tests and the multiple regression models, we used PROC GLM (General Linear Model Procedure) to construct general linear models and PROC GLIMMIX (Generalised Linear Mixed Model Procedure) (see, Dornmann *et al.*, 2007; Bolker *et al.*, 2008) to take spatial autocorrelation models fitting an exponential spatial covariance matrix to the data into account. Spatial autocorrelation can be defined as the patterns in which nearby observations are likely to have similar observation magnitudes than expected by chance (Legendre, 1993). This is mainly because processes that determine species richness such as dispersal are very contiguous in nature (Legendre & Legendre, 1998; Fortin & Dale, 2005), thus invalidating one of the most important assumptions in

statistics and ecology; that of the independence of errors (Legendre, 1993; Legendre & Legendre, 1998; Diniz-Fihlo *et al.*, 2003; Kuhn, 2007). SAS v9.2 package was used for all statistical analyses.

RESULTS

The current conservation portfolio only moderately captures anuran species distribution (Table 1). The average proportion of distribution accounted for by the current conservation portfolio ranges from 9.51% (stream-breeders) to 16.77% (temporary aquatic-breeders). Of the 239 species considered, 33 species ($\approx 14\%$) are not represented in the current conservation portfolio (Appendix 1), 24 of these species are permanent aquatic-, 4 temporary aquatic-, 3 stream- and 2 terrestrial-breeding groups. In addition, 34 species are classified as range-restricted, 13 of which are terrestrial-, 5 stream-, 8 temporary aquatic- and 8 permanent aquatic-breeding species. Range-restricted species were identified as species with a total geographical range of $< 20\,000\text{ km}^2$ (Alexander *et al.*, 2004).

The relationship between areas where different frog-breeding groups occur and the proportion of protected areas per grid cell was relatively weak (Table 2). A weak positive relationship was found for areas where permanent- and temporary-aquatic breeders occur; the relationship was largely negative for the ‘protected areas only (PA-only) models’ before and after controlling for spatial autocorrelation (Table 2). We found a non-significant negative relationship between areas where stream-breeders occur and the proportion of protected areas per grid cell (Table 2; Figure 1a). Terrestrial-breeders were negatively correlated with the proportion of protected areas per grid cell before and after controlling for spatial autocorrelation. In addition, this relationship became significantly negative after controlling for spatial autocorrelation and after taking other environmental variables into account (Table 3), for ‘both protected and unprotected areas model’.

The 84% parameter estimates of the PA-only model overlapped with the ‘protected and unprotected areas’ model for areas where stream- and temporary-aquatic breeding species occur (Table 4). There was no overlap between both ‘protected and unprotected areas’ and ‘protected areas only’ for areas where permanent aquatic- and terrestrial-breeding species occur (Table 4). The form of the relationship did not change after considering other environmental variables at least for areas where permanent aquatic-breeders occur (Table 3). For areas where temporary aquatic-breeders occur, the relationship became positive after accounting for other environmental variables and spatial autocorrelation for the ‘PA-only model’ (Table 3).

After excluding the wider unprotected matrix, the model strength decreased significantly for areas where stream-, permanent- and temporary-aquatic breeders occur. These results are true for both

the spatial and the non-spatial models, and both before and after taking environmental variables into account (Tables 2 & 3). For the protected area only model in terrestrial-breeders, the model strength showed an increase compared to the protected and unprotected area model, although the sign of the relationship remained negative (Table 2; Figure 1d). Following our model selection procedure, the best model predicting species richness of permanent-, temporary- aquatic and terrestrial-breeders, was found to be the model that included all variables (proportion of protected areas per grid cell, primary productivity, soil type diversity and range of elevation). The respective Akaike weights (w_i) for these models were (0.72, 0.6 and 0.9) (Table 3). The best model predicting the richness of stream-breeders was the model that included PPA, primary productivity, soil type diversity as covariates, with an Akaike weight (w_i) of 0.49.

DISCUSSION

The current southern African sub-continental portfolio of protected areas moderately captures amphibian diversity (Table 1). However, Seymour *et al.* (2001) concluded that current southern African sub-continental conservation portfolio was inadequate for conserving anurans as less than 35% of the amphibian diversity was accounted for by the conservation network (compared to $\approx 86\%$ in the current analysis). This seemingly large disparity in the number of species protected arises largely from the differences in analysis and spatial grains considered in the two studies. Seymour *et al.* (2001) classified grid cells to be protected if 50% or more of that particular grid cell was congruent with protected areas (however, see Mokhatla *et al.*, 2012 (Chapter 2) for limitations on such analyses). This is despite the large number of small-sized protected areas in the sub-region (Siegfried, 1987; Rebelo, 1997).

Our analysis indicates that the occurrence terrestrial-breeding species are negatively correlated with the current conservation portfolio (Table 2) and are not better represented in protected areas than would be expected by chance (Table 4). This negative relationship between the proportion of protected areas per grid cell and terrestrial-breeding species richness may be due to terrestrial-breeding frogs having characteristically small ranges, thus reducing their chances of being captured by the conservation portfolio (see Rodrigues *et al.*, 2004), although this needs to be explored further (i.e., to what extent does small distribution contributes to a species not being covered by protected areas, particularly terrestrial-breeding frogs). Another factor may be that the focus of assigning protected areas in the subcontinent was biased towards other habitat types such as riparian zones, and high altitude sites, as well as forested habitat types, as was the case for South Africa (Rebelo, 1997).

Due to the recent global amphibian declines, numerous studies have set out to identify species attributes common for most declining species or populations. These have been found to range from association with high altitudes, aquatic (stream) tadpole stage, restricted distribution, and small clutch sizes (Green, 2003; Lips *et al.*, 2003; Hero *et al.*, 2005; Kriger & Hero, 2007; Cooper *et al.*, 2008; Sodhi *et al.*, 2008; see also Whitton *et al.*, 2012). However, the relationship between the likelihood of decline and terrestrial-breeding amphibians is less clear (see Rovito *et al.*, 2009). Hero *et al.* (2005) reported that only 1 out of 20 terrestrial-breeding species was declining compared to 20 out of 40 species with an aquatic tadpole stage in upland areas of eastern Australia. Whitfield *et al.* (2007) found that both terrestrial-breeding amphibians and reptile species were declining at an equally alarming rate and this was attributed mainly to climate change-mediated reduction in the availability of leaf litter at their study site in Costa Rica. In addition, Hof *et al.* (2011) suggested that climate change, acting in synergy with anthropogenic-driven habitat alterations, are likely to be important threats affecting sub-Saharan amphibian biodiversity in future. Indeed, this seeming disparity from global trends (the relative importance of terrestrial-breeding species in conservation priority) is mainly because amphibian species declines in other parts of the world are thought to be driven by the occurrence of the amphibian chytrid fungus (Berger *et al.*, 1998; Hero *et al.*, 2005; Pounds *et al.*, 2006; Skerratt *et al.*, 2007). Although the fungus has been found in Africa (Hopkins & Channing, 2003; Blackburn *et al.*, 2010; Kielgast *et al.*, 2010; Bell *et al.*, 2011; Conradie *et al.*, 2011), it has not yet been linked with significant population declines.

Theoretically, species richness should increase with an increase in suitable available area (see Evans *et al.*, 2006; Jackson *et al.*, 2008; 2009). This is mainly because protected areas provide environments within which factors such as habitat destruction are either reduced or kept to a minimum (e.g., Bruner *et al.*, 2001). We however, found that the relationship between species richness and the proportion of protected areas per grid cell varied according to the area where different frog breeding-groups occur (Table 2). For protected areas only models, we found that the form of the relationship varied from a non-significant positive relationship for areas where permanent aquatic-breeding species occur (non-spatial model) to largely negative relationships for areas where permanent-aquatic and terrestrial-breeding species occur (both spatial and non-spatial) and areas where temporary aquatic-breeding species occur (Table 2). This suggests that areas of high species richness, particularly for areas where permanent aquatic- and terrestrial-breeding species occur are largely biased towards small-sized protected areas. This is despite the known concerns associated with small-sized protected areas (Parks & Harcourt, 2002; Chown *et al.*, 2003; Luck, 2007).

The interplay between the moderate representation of species distribution and the primarily negative relationship found between anuran species richness and the proportion of protected areas per grid cell suggest that small-sized protected areas are contributing significantly to conserving anuran

biodiversity in the sub-region (see also Evans *et al.*, 2006a). This association could however be coincidental (Araújo 2003). It is suggested that small-sized protected areas are more species-rich because they are more likely to be situated in areas of high primary productivity (e.g., Luck, 2007), known to be a significant correlate of species richness patterns. However, small-sized protected areas are also known to be surrounded areas with significantly higher human population growth rates (Chown *et al.*, 2003; Luck, 2007; Luck *et al.*, 2010; see also Wittemyer *et al.*, 2008). In addition, edge effects associated with land-use activities around protected areas and biological invasions, seem to be more pronounced for small-sized protected areas (Parks & Harcourt, 2002; Hansen & de Fries, 2007; Jackson & Gaston, 2008; Jackson *et al.*, 2009a).

The strength of the model of the relationship between species richness and the proportion of protected areas per grid cell largely decreased when the wider unprotected matrix was excluded from the model and increased when these were included (Table 2 & 3). Several other studies (focusing on different taxa) have found similar results (Evans *et al.*, 2006a; Jackson *et al.*, 2008; 2009, see also von May *et al.*, 2009). These relationships persisted after taking environmental variables known to influence species richness patterns into consideration (Seymour *et al.*, 2001; Jackson *et al.*, 2009). These results suggest that there are areas outside of “statutory” protected areas where amphibian diversity still survives. Indeed, recent evidence suggests that current conservation targets could be improved significantly if conservation efforts were to be merged with surrounding compatible land use activities such as private conservation areas (Gallo *et al.*, 2009; O’Connor & Kurley, 2009; Cox & Underwood, 2011 see also Fahrig *et al.*, 2011). Milner & Bennett (2007) found that riparian habitats, within surrounding agricultural landscapes would more likely function as corridors connecting areas of suitable habitats. In addition, Maritz & Alexander (2007) found that riparian zones within agricultural landscapes, in Mtunzini, (Kwa-Zulu Natal Province, South Africa), were more species-rich compared to nearby non-riparian habitats.

Current biological conservation literature suggests that conservation action be stream-lined with compatible land-use activities (Gallo *et al.*, 2009; O’Connor & Kurley, 2009; Cox & Underwood, 2011, see also Fahrig *et al.*, 2011). This is mainly because climate change and human-mediated land use activities are likely to be the two most important threats for amphibians in the southern African sub-continent (Hof *et al.*, 2011; see also Minter, 2011). Thus, it is not known whether the current static portfolio of protected areas will be sufficient to conserve biodiversity in the light of such expected species movements resulting from changes in climate (Minter, 2011). This becomes more pertinent given that it is thought that slightly over 60% of South African anuran species have recently suffered species range retractions (Botts *et al.*, 2012). Alternatively, it has been argued that there is perhaps a need to shift from the current static to a non-static conservation approach by developing either dynamic systems of protected areas (see Pressey *et al.*, 2007; Rayfield *et al.*, 2008; Hole *et al.*,

2011), or by locating protected areas where they are more likely to be climatically suitable as a result of climate change (D'Amen *et al.*, 2011).

In conclusion, this study highlighted that the current sub-continental portfolio of conservation areas is not sufficient to protect the whole suite of anuran biodiversity in southern Africa, and only moderately captures the proportion of species distribution. This is very important given the increased role that protected areas will play (e.g., Fabricius *et al.*, 2003; Jackson *et al.*, 2009b) in the light of the nature and the extent of threats anurans in the sub-continent are likely to face (Hof *et al.*, 2011), with terrestrial-breeding species likely to be at more risk. Although these results seem rather surprising as compared to global trends, it should be acknowledged that the effects of the chytrid fungus are not as pronounced in African (Hopkins & Channing, 2003; Weldon *et al.*, 2004; Blackburn *et al.*, 2010; Kielgast *et al.*, 2010; Bell *et al.*, 2011; Conradie *et al.*, 2011) as they are elsewhere (although further studies are needed to quantify this). In addition to aquatic breeding species, the current study identified the need to consider threats to biodiversity in a sub-continental context and prioritising conservation actions based on these.

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Table 1. Mean proportion of southern African amphibian species distribution protected per area where different frog breeding habitat groups occur.

Areas where different frog breeding-groups occur	Proportion of species distribution protected (Mean \pm SE)
Stream-breeders	9.51 \pm 2.88
Permanent aquatic-breeders	12.14 \pm 1.12
Temporary aquatic-breeders	16.78 \pm 1.31
Terrestrial-breeders	14.31 \pm 2.22

SE = Standard error

Table 2. Univariate regression models (both spatial and non-spatial) explaining the relationship between frog-breeding habitat groups and the proportion of protected area per grid cell in southern Africa.

Frog breeding-groups	Grid cells included	Model type	Proportion of protected land per grid cell	Model fit /AIC
Stream-breeders	Protected & unprotected	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,217)} = 3.36$ ns-	$r^2 = 1.5\%$
		Spatial	$F_{(1,217)} = 3.73$ ns-	AIC = 1288.9
	Protected only	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,151)} = 1.25$ ns-	$r^2 = 0.82\%$
		Spatial	$F_{(1,151)} = 1.61$ ns-	AIC = 984.9
Permanent aquatic-breeders	Protected & unprotected	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,8320)} = 188.08$ +++	$r^2 = 2.21\%$
		Spatial	$F_{(1,8320)} = 52.63$ ---	AIC = 33331.8
	Protected only	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,2814)} = 26.93$ ---	$r^2 = 0.95\%$
		Spatial	$F_{(1,2814)} = 82.78$ ---	AIC = 13250.5
Temporary aquatic-breeders	Protected & unprotected	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,8315)} = 364.77$ +++	$r^2 = 4.2\%$
		Spatial	$F_{(1,8315)} = 42.52$ ---	AIC = 32364.7
	Protected only	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,2813)} = 0.32$ ns+	$r^2 = 0.01\%$

Frog breeding-groups	Grid cells included	Model type	Proportion of protected land per grid cell	Model fit /AIC
		Spatial	$F_{(1,2813)} = 78.68$ ---	AIC = 12876.9
Terrestrial-breeders	Protected & unprotected	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,6294)} = 9.44$ --	$r^2 = 0.15$ %
		Spatial	$F_{(1,6294)} = 85.72$ ---	AIC = 29644.7
	Protected only	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,2568)} = 125.32$ ---	$r^2 = 4.56$ %
		Spatial	$F_{(1,2568)} = 75.82$ ---	AIC = 13019.6

Positive effects +++ $P < 0.001$, ++ $P < 0.01$, + $P < 0.05$; ns+ non-significant positive. Negative effects --- $P < 0.001$, -- $P < 0.01$, - $P < 0.05$, ns = non-significant negative.

Table 3. Multivariate correlations (both spatial and non-spatial models) explaining the relationship between frog-breeding habitat groups and the proportion of protected land per grid cell in southern Africa, while taking primary productivity, soil type diversity, and range of elevation into consideration.

Frog-breeding groups [and grid cells included]	Model type	Proportion of protected land per grid cell	Mean annual NPP	Soil type	Range of elevation	Model (fit: type)/AIC (model weight)
<i>Stream-breeders</i>						
[Protected & unprotected]	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,212)} = 1.94$ ns-	$F_{(1,212)} = 2.53$ ns-	$F_{(1,212)} = 0.75$ ns-	$F_{(1,212)} = 0.71$ ns-	$r^2 = 4.09\%$
	Spatial	$F_{(1,212)} = 8.39$ --	$F_{(1,212)} = 65.25$ ---	$F_{(1,212)} = 6.80$ --	$F_{(1,212)} = 1.21$ ns+	AIC = 1220.1 (0.33)
[Protected only]	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,147)} = 0.76$ ns-	$F_{(1,147)} = 2.77$ ns+	$F_{(1,147)} = 0.04$ ns-	$F_{(1,147)} = 0.00$ ns+	$r^2 = 2.72\%$
	Spatial	$F_{(1,147)} = 2.82$ ns-	$F_{(1,147)} = 60.58$ ---	$F_{(1,147)} = 4.67$ -	$F_{(1,147)} = 0.33$ ns+	AIC = 928.1 (0.14)

Frog-breeding groups [and grid cells included]	Model type	Proportion of protected land per grid cell	Mean annual NPP	Soil type	Range of elevation	Model (fit: type)/AIC (model weight)
<i>Permanent aquatic-breeders</i>						
[Protected & unprotected]	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,8315)} = 320.55$ +++	$F_{(1,8315)} = 5875.67$ +++	$F_{(1,8315)} = 313.43$ +++	$F_{(1,8315)} = 4.38$ +	$r^2 = 48.04$ %
	Spatial	$F_{(1,8315)} = 34.06$ ---	$F_{(1,8315)} = 40.84$ +++	$F_{(1,8315)} = 3.83$ +	$F_{(1,8315)} = 18.84$ +++	AIC =33276.1 (0.72)
[Protected only]	GLM	$F_{(1,2809)} = 2.08$ ns +	$F_{(1,2809)} = 965.84$ +++	$F_{(1,2809)} = 146.01$ +++	$F_{(1,2809)} = 0.04$ ns-	$r^2 = 30.7$ %
	Spatial	$F_{(1,2809)} = 70.98$ ---	$F_{(1,2809)} = 3.47$ ns+	$F_{(1,2809)} = 4.56$ +	$F_{(1,2809)} = 5.97$ +	AIC =13242.1 (0.49)

Frog-breeding groups [and grid cells included]	Model type	Proportion of protected land per grid cell	Mean annual NPP	Soil type	Range of elevation	Model (fit: type)/AIC (model weight)
<i>Temporary aquatic-breeders</i>						
[Protected & unprotected]	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,8310)} = 499.25$ +++	$F_{(1,8310)} = 3190.16$ +++	$F_{(1,8310)} = 189.5$ +++	$F_{(1,8310)} = 9.81$ --	$r^2 = 35.5$ %
	Spatial	$F_{(1,8310)} = 20.74$ ---	$F_{(1,8310)} = 62.62$ +++	$F_{(1,8310)} = 5.11$ +	$F_{(1,8310)} = 13.15$ +++	AIC = 32284.6 (0.82)
[Protected only]	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,2808)} = 42.27$ +++	$F_{(1,2808)} = 606.93$ +++	$F_{(1,2808)} = 85.8$ +++	$F_{(1,2808)} = 3.61$ ns-	$r^2 = 21.3$ %
	Spatial	$F_{(1,2808)} = 59.11$ ---	$F_{(1,2808)} = 3.94$ +	$F_{(1,2808)} = 5.16$ +	$F_{(1,2808)} = 11.70$ +++	AIC = 12862.6 (0.60)

Frog-breeding groups [and grid cells included]	Model type	Proportion of protected land per grid cell	Mean annual NPP	Soil type	Range of elevation	Model (fit: type)/AIC (model weight)
<i>Terrestrial-breeders</i>						
[Protected & unprotected]	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,6289)} = 1.67$ ns+	$F_{(1,6289)} = 852.05$ +++	$F_{(1,6289)} = 63.34$ +++	$F_{(1,6289)} = 37.6$ +++	$r^2 = 14.9\%$ AIC = 29610.9 (0.77)
	Spatial	$F_{(1,6289)} = 90.76$ ---	$F_{(1,6289)} = 6.70$ --	$F_{(1,6289)} = 5.32$ -	$F_{(1,6289)} = 28.87$ +++	
[Protected only]	Non-spatial	$F_{(1,2563)} = 33.95$ ---	$F_{(1,2563)} = 404.06$ +++	$F_{(1,2563)} = 43.37$ +++	$F_{(1,2563)} = 32.89$ +++	$r^2 = 20.5\%$ AIC = 12954.3 (0.90)
	Spatial	$F_{(1,2563)} = 91.55$ ---	$F_{(1,2563)} = 37.27$ ---	$F_{(1,2563)} = 6.22$ -	$F_{(1,2563)} = 28.33$ +++	

Positive effects +++ $P < 0.001$, ++ $P < 0.01$, + $P < 0.05$; ns+ non-significant positive. Negative effects --- $P < 0.001$, -- $P < 0.01$, - $P < 0.05$, ns- non-significant negative.

Table 4. Relationship between frog species richness and proportion of protected areas per grid cell in southern Africa for each of the frog-breeding groups examined. Models are based on grid cells representing both protected and unprotected areas, and those representing protected areas only. Any overlap in the 84% confidence interval values for a given breeding-group indicates that there are no statistically significant differences between models.

Frog-breeding habitat groups	Grid cells included	Slope estimate	Confidence interval
Stream-breeders	Protected & unprotected	0.0001	-0.0009 – 0.0011
	Protected only	-0.001	-0.0023 – 0.00023
Permanent aquatic-breeders	Protected & unprotected	-0.2	-0.33 – -0.061
	Protected only	-0.016	-0.018 – -0.011
Temporary aquatic-breeders	Protected & unprotected	-0.09	-0.23 – 0.06
	Protected only	0.0009	-0.003 – 0.005
Terrestrial-breeders	Protected & unprotected	-0.0008	-0.002 – 0.00005
	Protected only	-0.006	-0.007 – -0.006

Figure 1. Patterns indicating non-spatial, protected areas only relationships between anuran species richness based on four (A to D) areas where different frog-breeding groups occur in southern Africa and species richness of different frog breeding-groups. A = stream-breeding species, B = permanent aquatic-breeding species, C = temporary aquatic-breeding species, D = terrestrial-breeding species.

Figure 1A.

Figure 1B.

Figure 1C.

Figure 1D.

CHAPTER 4

General Discussion

Concluding remarks

Conservation of amphibians present a unique challenge to conservation biologists and practitioners as most amphibians display a bi-phasic life cycle; that is breeding, eggs and larvae are usually aquatic and the non-breeding foraging adult life stage is most often terrestrial. This presents a challenge about which type of habitat to prioritise. For example, an action such as land-clearing may prove beneficial to one stage of the life cycle and detrimental to the other for members of the same species (see Semlitsch *et al.*, 2009). Several recent studies have identified that imperilled amphibian share certain similar characteristics (Green, 2003; Lips *et al.*, 2003; Hero *et al.*, 2005; Bielby *et al.*, 2006; Kriger & Hero, 2007; Cooper *et al.*, 2008; Sodhi *et al.*, 2008; see also Whitton *et al.*, 2012). These studies identified aquatic-breeding amphibians, with mostly stream-adapted tadpoles, large adult body size, restricted distribution as well as small clutch sizes as factors associated with declines. It should be noted however that when relating particular threats to declining species, most studies have focused on ‘enigmatic declines’ associated threats such as chytrid fungus and the overall impacts of global climate change (e.g., Pounds *et al.*, 2006).

It is now generally accepted that each amphibian life history traits is affected differently by different anthropogenic threats (Becker *et al.*, 2007; Becker *et al.*, 2010). In exploring this further, and with reference to the southern African amphibian fauna, this thesis attempted to address amphibian conservation needs in southern Africa, by grouping species according to their breeding habitats. Following on from previous studies (particularly Whitfield *et al.*, 2007; Rovito *et al.*, 2009, but see also Hero *et al.*, 2005; Lips *et al.*, 2006; Gründler *et al.*, 2012), this thesis highlighted that unlike elsewhere, in southern Africa terrestrial-breeding species have an increased need for conservation action due to anthropogenic-driven threatening processes such as land-use transformation and alien invasive plant species. This is true for both terrestrial- as well as stream-breeding species at both the national and the biogeographical scales. These threats are further intensified by the inability of the current protected areas portfolio to capture a full suite of amphibian diversity with particular reference to terrestrial-breeding amphibians. While considering both terrestrial- and aquatic-breeding species in one analysis, this study is the first in Africa to find that terrestrial-breeding species have an elevated conservation concern in comparison with aquatic-breeding species. However, it is acknowledged that the lack of aquatic-related anthropogenic threats modelled (as well as other reasons, see chapter 2 Discussion) might have a significant bearing to the results and thus their interpretation.

In addition to the availability of aquatic-related threat variables (see Discussion of Chapter) a further limitation of this analysis is the unavailability of similar anthropogenic threats at the same spatial scale for other African countries. This limits the conclusions that can be drawn at the sub-continental scale in this thesis. However, several studies have reported on the observed pattern of high spatial overlaps between biodiversity and humans for sub-Saharan Africa (see Balmford *et al.*, 2001; Fjeldså & Burgess 2008) particularly at broad spatial scales. Furthermore, possible mechanisms driving this pattern have been reported in Africa (Hugo & van Rensburg, 2008) and Australia (Luck *et al.*, 2010). It is further suggested that human population densities are directly correlated with the number and diversity of alien species (Gaston, 2005). In addition to changes in land-use practises (see Stuart *et al.*, 2004, see also Hof *et al.*, 2011), biological invasions are one of the most intensifying threats to biodiversity (see McGeoch *et al.*, 2010) including amphibians (see Li *et al.* 2011; Mokhatla *et al.*, 2012, Chapter 2). This study also highlighted the paucity of knowledge, particularly on how biological invasions, through alien invasive plants species affect amphibians (also see Martin & Murray, 2011).

Recommendations and future research directions

Challenges facing amphibian conservation in South Africa (and possibly the southern African sub-continent) include the dwindling numbers of professional herpetologists employed in universities and conservation agencies, limited opportunities of luring new graduate students in studying herpetology as well as the lack of programmes aimed at increasing the interest of the general public to amphibians, their importance as well as highlighting their current plight (Tolley *et al.* 2011). This is compounded by a lack of long-term ecological monitoring programmes (Measey *et al.*, 2011), which are of critical importance to differentiate between local-level population fluctuations as well as real species extinctions. This thesis identified the need to document as well as establish causal links between anthropogenic-induced threats (such as alien invasive plants and different land uses) and the mechanisms underlying anuran species decline in their midst. This is because in the main, coincidence alone does not provide causal links with declining species and populations. There is also a need for more accurate species distribution data, more so for terrestrial-breeding species, seeing that these were more likely to be congruent with anthropogenic threats at both the national and biogeographical scales in addition to showing a negative relationship with the proportion of protected areas per grid cell. In addition, studies on the effectiveness of the protected areas portfolio on biodiversity will be of more benefit if the comparisons were made between either different time frames or temporal intervals, in the light of threats such as alien plant species, land uses and global climate change, in addition to 'space for time replacements' currently employed in Chapter 3 (Chown, 2010).

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APPENDIX

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